

BE OPEN project
“European forum and oBsErVatory for OPEN science in transport”

Advisory Board
Terms of Reference

PREAMBLE

Open Science is a modern movement that represents a new approach to practicing science, in a way that increases openness, integrity and reproducibility of research. It aims at making scientific process and results more transparent and accessible at all levels and to everyone. The rapid growth of digital technologies and new collaborative tools become enablers of Open Science, allowing to speed up the process of adopting open habits and facilitating the sharing of large volumes of information, study materials and data. Europe has the culture and ability to share research activities across national boundaries, which along with its remarkable research and knowledge base, put it in a leading position in the world to promote and expedite the new Open Science way of working.

The [BE-OPEN project](#) aims to assist in operationalising Open Science in transport research at the European level, through a series of targeted coordination and support activities.

BE OPEN is a 30-month Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action that started in January 2019, and addresses the [call MG-4-2-2018 Building Open Science platforms in transport research](#).

ARTICLE 1 – Purpose and role of the Advisory Board

The Advisory Board consists of independent experts with wide recognition and proven expertise in the fields of transport research, open science, or international cooperation.

Its role is:

- a) to ensure that the BE OPEN Consortium is progressing along the correct path;
- b) to provide feedback at key project milestones;
- c) to support the critical actions implemented within the project;
- d) and to be informed about the corresponding results.

ARTICLE 2 – Membership of the Advisory Board

The Advisory Board consists of eight (8) members, including a Chairperson.

All members are appointed by the BE OPEN Steering Committee based on interest and mutual agreement for a period of one year.

The membership may end in case of voluntary retirement or revocation of the appointment. In that case, the BE OPEN Steering Committee, will assess the need of a successor and appoint another person for the remaining term.

ARTICLE 3 – Advisory Board Chairperson

The Advisory Board is presided by a Chairperson, who is nominated by the Steering Committee based on interest and mutual agreement.

The role of the Chairperson is:

- a) to actively manage the BE OPEN Advisory Board, in view to achieve its given role,
- b) to hold close contacts with the BE OPEN Advisory Board Liaison and Coordinator,
- c) to inform and report to the BE OPEN Steering Committee. He/She may be represented by another member of the Advisory Board,
- d) To chair the AB meeting.

ARTICLE 4 – Rules of procedure of the Advisory Board

The following rules of procedure will apply to the Advisory Board:

4.1 Meetings

The Advisory Board will convene during its mandate at two relevant key project milestones, in addition to a brief introductory session.

The invitation for Advisory Board meetings will be addressed by the BE OPEN coordinator to the Advisory Board members at least 30 days before the meeting. The invitation shall include a draft agenda along with all necessary documents. The Advisory Board may meet via electronic means, notably by teleconference.

The meetings of the Advisory Board and its resolutions shall be recorded by the Chairperson with the assistance of a person appointed by the BE OPEN coordinator. The meeting minutes shall be circulated to the Advisory Board within a month after the meeting. Once approved a copy shall be kept by the BE OPEN consortium.

During its mandate, the Advisory Board is expected to convene at the following project key moments:

- In Fall 2020 for a first introductory meeting via conference call;
- In January/February 2021 along with the second BE OPEN workshop (online);
- In April/May 2020 along with the BE OPEN final event (online).

4.2 Costs of participation by Advisory Board members

Any travel, accommodation and registration costs incurred for participating in the Advisory Board meetings (two meetings) or BE OPEN events are covered by the BE OPEN project.

The Advisory Board member shall travel in economy class where available. First or business class flight tickets are not reimbursable; accommodation booking shall be made on the same basis.

Booking of flights/train, accommodation or registration shall be made by the Advisory Board member in accordance with the dates of the meeting or event.

A reimbursement form will be given to the Advisory Board member. This form is to be filled out, stating the costs in the national currency if applicable, and in Euro. All reimbursements will be made in Euro to the bank account to be provided on the form by the AB member.

Reimbursement will be made on the basis of original receipts and justifications. Therefore, the AB Member shall keep all original invoices including flight boarding passes, local public transport tickets or registration receipt. These documents must be sent along with the reimbursement form as proof.

The form is to be signed by hand and sent by mail or alike together with all documents mentioned above within 30 days after the meeting to the following address: ECTRI c/o POLIS, rue du Trône 98, 1050 Brussels, Belgium.

The costs of time spent by the Members to conduct the tasks described in article 2 are not covered by the BE OPEN project.

ARTICLE 5 – Mandate of the Advisory Board

The mandate is for one year, starting on July 1st, 2020, and ending on June 30th, 2021.